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**FACING OF DISPUTE AND THEIR
MANAGEMENT WHILE ONLINE
TEACHING BY TEACHERS : A QUAN-qual
STUDY**

Authors &
Affiliations:

¹ Asadullah

*Ph.D. Scholar, Institute of Education and Research,
Muslim Youth University Islamabad, Pakistan.*

² Salma Shahzadi

*Ph.D. Scholar, Institute of Education and Research,
Muslim Youth University Islamabad, Pakistan*

³ Asia Rubab

*Ph.D. Scholar, Institute of Education and Research,
Muslim Youth University, Islamabad, Pakistan.*

Email Add:

¹ asadlakho642@gmail.com

² hinaf4543@gmail.com

³ asiarubab87@gmail.com

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*Asadullah

**Salma Shahzadi

***Asia Rubab

ABSTRACT

Our daily life is full of disputes in various aspects. These cannot be avoided, but can be managed in befitting manner to overcome the issues amicably. A Quan-qual study on “Conflicts faced by teachers and their management styles during online teaching” with objectives of (i) To identify conflicts faced by teachers during online teaching. (ii) To investigate management strategies used by teachers during online teaching is carried out. Mixed methods are used and sequential explanatory design is used. Survey method is used for data collection for quantitative and interview technique has been used for qualitative data. 694 teaching staff from Private universities of Islamabad has been analyzed. Sample was 20% of the total population which was 139. For qualitative result purpose 10% of data is collected through interviews while Proportionate Accidental sampling technique has been used. For quantitative results, data is analyzed by using mean, mode and standard deviation and for qualitative results, data was analyzed by thematic method.

Key words: Conflict, Conflict Management Strategies, teaching, education, teachers.

INTRODUCTION

Conflicts during online teaching

Conflict means clash, discord or incompatibility. Wherever, multiple stakeholders work together, conflict arises. Management is an organization and manages conflicts. There are conflicts everywhere in the world. One cannot deny the existence of conflicts. The important thing is to manage conflicts in such a way that conflicts are resolved without escalating and harming others. In discussing the facing of conflicts, it is important to review the online style of teaching and subsequently the management of conflicts by teachers. In contrast, current management styles will also be discussed to draw comparisons between the two and highlight the management styles used in online education. Their potential benefit to developing students and negative input to their academic performance will also be examined.

* Ph.D Scholar, Institute of Education and Research, Muslim Youth University Islamabad, Pakistan.

**Ph.D Scholar, Institute of Education and Research, Muslim Youth University Islamabad, Pakistan.

***Ph.D Scholar, Institute of Education and Research, Muslim Youth University, Islamabad, Pakistan.

Worth of the Study

This study prove to be helpful for teachers doing online teaching, students learning online and relevant educational authorities to include syllabus regarding conflicts and its management during online teaching for better training and guidance of teaching staff. It will be an effort to promote online education by getting constructive outcomes of conflicts. Study will also benefit all teaching staff at university and various other levels and practically guide to solve conflicts during online teaching, being faced by teachers.

Objectives of the Study

- i) To identify conflicts faced by teachers during online teaching.
- ii) To investigate management strategies used by teachers during online teaching.

Research Question(s)

- i) What are the types of conflicts being faced by teachers?
- ii) What are the conflicts management strategies used by teachers during online teaching?

Delimitation of Study

This study was surrounded to Private Universities of Islamabad for the Session 2021:

- i) Islamabad
- ii) Private Sector Universities
- iii) Session 2021

LITERATURE REVIEW**Conflicts defined by researchers**

It has been observed that conflicts are raised due to non adherence of skills of management. In fact, conflict is not a bad thing itself, but result of the conflicts directly depend on personal talent and managerial skill of an individual. ¹

Types Of conflicts

Conflicts can be between two groups, organizations, departments or between countries. When we talk about personnel, it may be their self interests. While we discuss about managers, making decisions is the reason, and between the organizations financial or business interest are the reasons. Conflict basing on the performance is related with the groups. Some of the other types are as under.

1. Intrapersonal Conflict

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2. Intergroup Conflict
3. Approach-avoidance conflict
4. Avoidance conflict
5. Approach-approach conflict
6. Intragroup Conflict
7. Interpersonal Conflict
8. Intra-Organizational Conflicts

Conflict is connected with poor decisions. Two types of conflict are usually associated with constant groups. Three definitions can be considered for this association, misclassification of task clash as relationship conflict, strict task conflict tactics that trigger association conflict, and misclassification of association conflict as work conflict.²

As per sociological term, focus is on conflict type, which arise among the societal units, i.e. between personnel, groups or institutions This type of conflicts are known as interpersonal, intergroup or interdepartmental or inter-organizational conflicts, correspondingly.³

Important factor is that a table showing the graphical illustration is clearly portraying the five conflict management styles is re-produced as under.⁴

Sources: Rahim (2002, p. 217); Boonsathorn (2007, p. 200)

Conflict Management Strategies⁵

1	2	3	4	5
Integrating Win-Win	Obliging Loose-Win	Compromising No Loose–No Win	Avoiding Loose–Loose	Dominating Win-Loose

Integrating

High concern for both i.e. self & others is characterized by distribution information widely, settling disputing beneficially, and ensuring utmost endeavor to arrive at a resolution which could be mutually satisfactory. Approach is much desirable due to reason that, same is much likely to outcome in a win-win solution, particularly in that situation which is acknowledged with enduring reliance on the opponent revelry. Furthermore, this diminishes intensity of task dispute and association conflict.

Obliging

This approach is thought to show more concern for the opposition and less worry for oneself. This emphasize to protect and maintain to interaction rather than accomplishment termination that satisfy the persons own concerns. In a situation where other party is right and dispute is very vital to the opponent party. This is more sensible to use a dutiful approach. When one party is in weak position and it is believed that leaving the conflict would lead to much favorable results and solution. In this situation it is suitable to practice this approach. In addition, certain circumstances such as time and pressure may cause a dutiful approach to be adopted.

Dominating

This style is known as win-lose strategy. It is appropriate to ignore the need and hope of opponent party and self interests, through power tactics, when matters of conflict engage usual matters or need a quick judgment.

Avoiding

This style provide results with some concern for self one or those of others. When issue in dispute is significant and needs immediate decision-making duty, withdrawing from the dispute may have detrimental consequences for all parties.

Compromising

It reflects a reasonable concern for a persons self interests and a reasonable concern for other persons interests. Results which can be mutually agreed upon by both parties, is a desired approach for resolving conflict. This style deals give and take. It makes sense to use this approach when, both side parties have same power position and cannot reach

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consensus. The main position in use of this approach is that, it fails in identifying actual, difficult troubles.⁶

Most conciliatory and integrative clash management strategies had been used by conflict managers of selected educational institutions. However, the conflict management style used during online teaching and learning processes can be careful and varied, due to the nature of the stakeholders' dealings. Some timed response in short form by teachers can cause great anxiety and on the other hand long statement without physical cues may not satisfy the respondent due to misunderstanding and facial expressions.⁷

A notable value of a good teacher is to be clear speaker. They alter their voice pitch and tonality in order to do this while instructing in schools. Pupils respond well to teachers who communicate with clarity and precision. Instructors ought to practice projecting their voices. They must be able to change volume, pitch and tone based on condition.

Expression's power discovers and exhibits mysterious associations between the created and creator. Expression's power is a quality of any individuals to have effect on many others.⁸

Many Recent studies have proved that

Individually, emotional intelligence (EI) is linked to scholastic success, productivity at work, the capacity for clear communication, problem-solving skills, and the development of deep interpersonal connections. For increasing understanding level of individuals' behave and their adoption to social environment, emotional intelligence is best potential.⁹

An account of helping to develop the human competencies in society, universities have played a major and significant role as academic institutions. Because of it, paying great attention towards them is very important and necessary. The rise in organizational dispute is one of major problems that all organizations, but especially the academic sector, are facing. Senior leaders are considering this issue because of its detrimental impact on declining efficiencies, increased divergence, and poor interpersonal communication.¹⁰

A researcher namely Robins has believed ,based on his research, public know factors generated by dispute, for instance, scarcity, blockage, and incompatible interest. Resource shortage, either monetary, job, prestige or power, encourages the obstruction of behavior and clash arises. dispute can also be broken out.¹¹

METHODOLOGY

Quan-qual research methodology has been used in this paper. Data collection is made by sample population through a questionnaire for quantitative and through interviews for qualitative research. After obtaining data, it was entered in the SPSS to evaluate the results of quantitative data. Thematic analysis for of results was done for qualitative results.

Research Design

Quan-qual research approach was adopted. Mixed methods were used and Sequential Explanatory design was used. Survey technique for quantitative and interview method for qualitative approach was used for data collection.

Study's population

private universities of Islamabad's teaching staff is the population, comprising number 694.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

Proportionate random sampling technique was used. Sample was 20% of the total population for current study, which was 139. For qualitative results 10% of data was collected through interviews which was 14.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

Quantitative Approach

Researcher have just used questionnaire as a tool for quantitative approach, to measure four dispute types. Questionnaire comprised 20 questions. Farooqi Organizational Conflict Inventory (FOCI) has been used to get objectives of study. Permission from the author of the inventory named as Dr. Muhammad Tahir Khan Farooqi. Questionnaire was got filled from teachers of sampled universities.

Qualitative Approach

For qualitative approach interview Performa was prepared to conduct the interviews form the population. Performa was consisting objectives wise questions. Response was assessed according to the themes. Response was observed in four categories from high to low i.e. Extremely, Mostly, Sometime and Once.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Table 1: Summarised frequency and percentages - Affective Conflict

S#	Categorizesump1Q1to5	Frequency	Percent(%)
1	Once in a While	52	31.6
2	Sometime	45	25.2
3	Fairly Often	38	22.4
4	Frequently if Not Often	39	20.8
	Total	174	100

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Table 1 showed the response of teaching staff in frequency and percentage of affective conflict after re-scaling the response from 5 likert scale to 4 likert scale.

Table 2: Summarised frequency and percentages - Substantive Conflict

S#	Categorizesump1Q6to10	Frequency	Percent(%)
1	Once in a While	38	22.2
2	Sometime	53	29.9
3	Fairly Often	42	24.7
4	Frequently if Not Often	41	23.2
Total		174	100

Table 2 showed the response of teaching staff in frequency and percentage of affective conflict after re-scaling the response from 5 likert scale to 4 likert scale.

Table 3: Summarised frequency and percentages - Institutionalized Conflict

S#	Categorizesump1Q11to15	Frequency	Percent(%)
1	Once in a While	47	27.6
2	Sometime	41	23.0
3	Fairly Often	45	26.5
4	Frequently if Not Often	41	22.9
Total		174	100

Table 3 showed the response of teaching staff in frequency and percentage of affective conflict after re-scaling the response from 5 likert scale to 4 likert scale.

Table 4: Summarised frequency and percentages - Realistic Conflict

S#	Categorizesump1Q16to20	Frequency	Percent(%)
1	Once in a While	47	27.8
2	Sometime	40	22.1
3	Fairly Often	53	30.3

4	Frequently if Not Often	34	19.8
Total		174	100

Table 4 showed the response of teaching staff in frequency and percentage of affective conflict after re-scaling the response from 5 likert scale to 4 likert scale.

Table 5: Summarised frequency and percentages - Conflicts

S#	Answer	Frequency	Percent(%)
1	Once in a While	48	26.0
2	Sometime	41	24.3
3	Fairly Often	46	26.7
4	Frequently if Not Often	39	23.0
Total		174	100

Table 5 showed the total response of teaching staff of all conflicts after re-scaling the response from 5 likert scale to 4 likert scale.

Table 6: Mean and SD of Respondents - Conflict faced by teachers

S#	Type of Conflict	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	Affective Conflict	2.3564	1.13258
2	Substantive Conflict	2.5058	1.07923
3	Institutionalized Conflict	2.4714	1.12605
4	Realistic Conflict	2.4484	1.08867

Table 6 showed the response of conflicts by the means of means and std deviation.

Table 7: Summarised response of dispute management strategies adopted by teachers

S#	Management Style	Percent(%)
1	Integrating Style	39.97058825
2	Obliging Style	53.64705883
3	Compromising Style	42.41176472
4	Avoiding Style	22.79411766
5	Dominating Style	15.17647058

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Total

174

Table 7 showed the response of respondents for conflicts management styles adopted by teaching staff by the means of Frequency and percentage.

4.2 Qualitative Data

Table 9: Summary of Results of Interviews – Qualitative Data

S#	Objective		Theme	Questions & Answers	n	Response	
1	Objective 1	i	Affective Conflict	To recognise types of disputes faced by teachers during online teaching.			
				Number of Questions	3	14	Once
		ii	Substantive Conflict	Number of Questions	3	14	Extremely
		iii	Institutionalized Conflict	Number of Questions	3	14	Mostly
		iv	Realistic Conflict	Number of Questions	3	14	Sometime
2	Objective 2	i	Integrating	To investigate conflict management styles adopted by teachers to manage disputes.			
				Number of Questions	3	14	Sometime
		ii	Obliging	Number of Questions	3	14	Extremely
		iii	Compromising	Number of Questions	3	14	Mostly
		iv	Avoiding	Number of Questions	3	14	Once
		v	Dominating	Number of Questions	3	14	Once

Conclusion

In first objective it has been concluded, most of the teachers faced Substantive Conflict ($M = 2.50$, $S.D = 1.07$). After that Institutionalized conflict was faced ($M = 2.47$, $S.D = 1.12$). After that, Realistic Conflict was faced ($M = 2.44$, $S.D = 1.08$) and in the last Affective conflict for which mean and SD value is ($M = 2.35$, $S.D = 1.13$).

In second objective, various teachers used Obliging strategy (53%) while managing the conflicts. After that Compromising (42%), Integrating (39%), Avoiding (22%) and Dominating (15%) conflict management strategy was used.

Findings

After analyzing the response by the respondents, data and results of first objective it has been found that, majority of teachers faced Substantive Conflict. In second number, institutionalized conflict was faced. After that, realistic conflict and in the last affective conflict was faced by the teaching staff during online teaching at university level. In second objective most of the teaching staff used obliging conflict management strategy. After that, they used compromising, integrating, avoiding and in the last, dominating conflict management strategy.

Recommendations

1. Integrating conflict management style may be focused by the teaching staff, due to reason that, this is a win-win situation and suitable for both the parties.
2. Avoiding conflict management style, as already used in very low cases, may be avoided at maximum level, and it must be ensured to reduce the conflict and measures for its eradication may be done, but, avoiding the conflict will further increase its intensity and re-occurrence.
3. Dominating conflict management style may not be used, as already used in the last category, for the establishing of good norms and listening to all stake holders in the educational institutions.

REFERENCES

- ¹Afzalur Rahim, M., David Antonioni, and Clement Psenicka. "A STRUCTURAL EQUATIONS MODEL OF LEADER POWER, SUBORDINATES' STYLES OF HANDLING CONFLICT, AND JOB PERFORMANCE." *International journal of conflict management* 12, no. 3 (2001): 195.
- ²Simons, Tony L., and Randall S. Peterson. "Task conflict and relationship conflict in top management teams: the pivotal role of intragroup trust." *Journal of applied psychology* 85, no. 1 (2000): 102.
- ³Wall Jr, James A., and Ronda Roberts Callister. "Conflict and its management." *Journal of management* 21, no. 3 (1995): 516.
- ⁴Afzalur Rahim, M. "Toward a theory of managing organizational conflict." *International journal of conflict management* 13, no. 3 (2002): 217.
- ⁵Afzalur Rahim, M., David Antonioni, and Clement Psenicka. "A STRUCTURAL EQUATIONS MODEL OF LEADER POWER, SUBORDINATES' STYLES OF HANDLING CONFLICT, AND JOB PERFORMANCE." 196, 207.

FACING OF DISPUTE AND THEIR MANAGEMENT WHILE ONLINE TEACHING BY TEACHERS: A QUAN- qual STUDY

- ⁶Rahim, M. Afzalur. *Managing conflict in organizations*. (Routledge, 1992) 371-375.
- ⁷Kiran, Sidra, and Almas IkramKayani. "Transformational Leadership As Mediating Factor Influencing Conflict Management and Performance of Teaching Faculty at Higher Education Level: A Study in Punjab, Pakistan." *Pakistan Social Sciences Review* 4, no. 2 (2020): 272-275.
- ⁸Farooqi, T, K, M., Arshad, F, Khan, M, A, H., and Ghaffar, A. "Interplay of Conflict Management Styles with Teachers' Performance". *International Journal of AYER*. (2015). Vol 1. p.309.
- ⁹Farooqi, Muhammad Tahir Khan, Fahim Arshad, Hafiz Muhammad Ather Khan, and Abdul Ghaffar. "Interplay of conflict management styles with teachers' performance." *International Journal of AYER* 1, no. 2 (2016): 305-320.
- ¹⁰ Majid, Fahim Aziz, and Ali Abdulhassan Abbas. "The Intermediary Effect of Organizational Chaos in the Relationship between Organizational Conflict and Psychological Empowerment." *THE IRAQI MAGAZINE FOR ADMINISTRATIVE SCIENCES* 13, no. 53 (2017): 217.
- ¹¹ Ikeda, Ana Akemi, Tania Modesto Veludo-de-Oliveira, and Marcos Cortez Campomar. "Organizational conflicts perceived by marketing executives." *EJBO-Electronic Journal of Business Ethics and Organization Studies* (2005). 25.